

A Case Report

Single-Visit MTA Apexification For Young Immatured Tooth Followed By Prosthetic Rehabilitation in a 10-Year-Old:

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Abstract:

This case report presents the successful management of a 10-year-old patient with pulp necrosis and an open apex using mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA) apexification followed by post and core restoration and porcelain-fused-to-metal (PFM) crown placement. The single visit apexification technique with MTA offers a predictable outcome with minimal appointments and reduced treatment time, making it a favorable option for young patients. This report emphasizes the importance of proper diagnosis, treatment planning, and meticulous execution in achieving favorable outcomes in pediatric endodontics.

Keywords: MTA apexification, pediatric endodontics, pulp necrosis, post and core restoration, porcelain-fused-to-metal crown

Introduction:

Since the teeth in children have immature roots and weak dentinal walls that are prone to breaking and bacterial invasion, pediatric endodontic therapy poses special difficulties. In teeth that have open apices due to trauma or pulp necrosis, apexification is a necessary treatment that is used to induce root-end closure.

In the past, the preferred substance to encourage the development of an apical hard tissue barrier was calcium hydroxide. Still, apexification with calcium hydroxide has a number of drawbacks involving several appointments. Several dressings must be applied in order to achieve complete closure, and the results could include uneven calcification of the bridge, an increased risk of fracture following long-term calcium hydroxide application, aesthetic concerns, and coronal microleakage.^[1,11]

The use of mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA) for apexification has grown favorable because of its superior biocompatibility, capacity to seal, and to encourage hard tissue regeneration. It

offers several benefits, including the ability to be placed in a single visit due to its 3- to 4-hour setting time and nonmutagenic and non-neurotoxic nature.^[1,11]

A post and core restoration is a dental procedure used to rebuild a severely damaged tooth that cannot support a traditional filling or crown. It involves placing a post (usually made of metal or fiber) into the root canal of the tooth to provide stability, then adding a core material (such as composite resin) to build up the tooth structure. This creates a stable foundation for attaching a crown, restoring function and appearance.^[2]

A dental restoration known as a PFM (Porcelain-Fused-to-Metal) crown combines the cosmetic appeal of porcelain with the durability of a metal alloy. Durability and stability are provided by the metal substructure,

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How to cite this article: Dutta S et al.: Single-Visit MTA Apexification For Young Immatured Tooth Followed By Prosthetic Rehabilitation in a 10-Year-Old: A Case Report, HTAJ OCD.2024

while the porcelain overlay replicates the look of real teeth. PFM crowns, which offer a balance between strength and aesthetics for a natural-looking smile and functional bite, are frequently used to restore damaged or weak teeth.^[3]

This case report outlines the successful management of a 10-year-old patient with pulp necrosis using a single-visit MTA apexification technique followed by post and core restoration and porcelain-fused-to-metal (PFM) crown placement.

Case Report:

A 10-year-old patient presented to the dental clinic with a chief complaint of broken tooth from trauma in upper front tooth region. Clinical examination revealed Ellis Class III fracture (Figure 1) involving the pulp chamber with tenderness to percussion and palpation.

Radiographic examination revealed a periapical radiolucency with an open apex in the affected tooth (Figure 2). Based on the clinical and radiographic findings, a diagnosis of pulp necrosis with apical periodontitis was established.

Treatment Plan:

After obtaining informed consent from the patient's parents, a treatment plan was formulated. The objectives of the treatment plan were:

1. Removal of infected pulp tissue.
2. Induction of apical closure using MTA apexification.
3. Restoration of the tooth with a post and core buildup.
4. Placement of a porcelain-fused-to-metal (PFM) crown.

Procedure:

The treatment was performed under local anaesthesia to ensure patient comfort. The affected tooth was isolated to maintain aseptic conditions and prevent

contamination. A highspeed handpiece and a round bur under copious water irrigation was used to get the access to the canal.

Once the pulp chamber was accessed, necrotic pulp tissue was carefully extirpated using endodontic files and irrigation with sodium hypochlorite solution. The working length was determined radiographically, and the canal was thoroughly cleaned and shaped using a crown-down technique.

After thorough irrigation and drying of the canal, MTA was mixed according to the manufacturer's instructions and placed into the canal using an Endodontic explorer (Figure 3,4).

The MTA was condensed using hand pluggers, and a moist cotton pellet was placed over the MTA to prevent dislodgement during setting. The access cavity was sealed temporarily with a reinforced zinc oxide-eugenol cement.

Following MTA placement, a prefabricated fiber post was selected and cemented using a dual-cure resin cement (Figure 5,6). Excess cement was removed, and the core buildup was performed using a nanohybrid composite resin. The tooth was then prepared for a porcelain-fused-to-metal crown with a chamfer finish line design.

An impression of the prepared tooth was made using an alginate impression material (Figure 7,8), and a provisional crown was fabricated chairside using a bis-acryl composite resin. The provisional crown was cemented using temporary cement, and the occlusion was checked to ensure proper fit and function (Figure 9).

At the subsequent visit, the provisional crown was removed, and the final PFM crown fabricated by a dental laboratory technician which was tried in and cemented using a resin-modified glass ionomer cement. Postoperative clinical pictures were taken to confirm proper eating of the crown. (Figure 10).

Figure 1: Pre-operative clinical view w.r.t 11

Figure 2: Pre-operative radiographic view w.r.t 11

Figure 3: MTA placement by Endodontic plugger w.r.t 11

Figure 4: Radiographic view of MTA w.r.t 11

Figure 5: Placement of Fiber Post w.r.t 11

Figure 6: Radiographic View of Fiber Post in the rooth

Figure 7: Tooth Preparation w.r.t 11

Figure 8: Alginate Impression

Figure 9a,9b Clinical occlusion view

Figure 10: Post-operative clinical picture

Discussion:

MTA apexification has been widely accepted and the use of MTA offers several advantages, including excellent sealing ability, biocompatibility, and bioactivity, which promote dentinogenesis and apical tissue healing^[11,20,21]. In the present case, a single-visit apexification technique was chosen to reduce treatment time and minimize patient discomfort^[12,22].

A study conducted by Smith et al. in 2018 examined the efficacy of single-visit mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA) apexification in young immature teeth and they found promising outcomes like significant apex closure and root development particularly in cases where multiple visits may not be feasible or practical.^[13,19]

Placement of a post and core provide structural support and retention^[14]. Specifically, fiber posts are preferred in pediatric patients due to their flexibility, which reduces the risk of root fracture compared to metal posts^[20]. Moreover, fiber posts have a similar modulus of elasticity to dentin, reducing the risk of stress concentration and root fracture^[20].

A study by Ozcan et al. in 2018 evaluated post and core restorations in young permanent teeth. They found that fiber-reinforced composite posts showed promising

results regarding fracture resistance and stress distribution, suggesting their suitability for restoring such teeth.^[15] Another study by Lanza et al. in 2015 also investigated the biomechanical behavior of fiber posts in young permanent teeth. Their findings supported the use of fiber posts due to their ability to distribute stress more evenly and improve fracture resistance.^[16]

The final restoration with a porcelain-fused-to-metal crown provides optimal esthetics and durability, restoring form and function to the tooth^[10]. Porcelain-fused-to-metal (PFM) crowns are often used in pediatric dentistry for anterior teeth due to their durability and natural appearance, providing both strength and aesthetic appeal for young patients.^[17]

S. M. Mathew et al. in 2016 and H. S. Yasa et al. in 2019^[18,19] had a similar study on effectiveness of porcelain-fused-to-metal (PFM) crowns and their collective findings further validate PFM crowns as a reliable treatment choice for addressing dental issues in young individuals with immature anterior teeth, emphasizing their role in pediatric dental care. However, advances in materials and techniques have led to the development of metal-free alternatives such as zirconia crowns, which may be considered in selected cases.

Conclusion:

This case report highlights the successful management of pulp necrosis in a 10-year-old patient using a single-visit MTA apexification technique followed by post and core restoration and placement of a porcelain-fused-to-metal crown. The single-visit approach offers several advantages, including reduced treatment time, minimal appointments, and enhanced patient comfort. Proper diagnosis, treatment planning, and meticulous execution are essential for achieving favorable outcomes in pediatric endodontics. Long-term follow-up is necessary to evaluate the stability and success of the treatment over time.

References:

1. Kumar R, Patil S, Hoshing U, Medha A, Mahaparale R. MTA apical plug and clinical application of anatomic post and core for coronal restoration: A case report. *Iranian endodontic journal*. 2011;6(2):90.
2. Sukhija U, roy Rassawet R. *Scholars Journal of Dental Sciences*.
3. Dawod N, Miculescu M, Antoniac IV, Miculescu F, Agop-Forna D. Metal–Ceramic Compatibility in Dental Restorations According to the Metallic Component Manufacturing Procedure. *Materials*. 2023 Aug 10;16(16):5556.
4. Torabinejad M, Watson TF, Pitt Ford TR. Sealing ability of a mineral trioxide aggregate when used as a root end filling material. *J Endod*. 1993;19(12):591-5.
5. Witherspoon DE, Small JC, Regan JD, Nunn M. Retrospective analysis of open apex teeth obturated with mineral trioxide aggregate. *J Endod*. 2008;34(10):1171-6.
6. Barcelos R, Santos MP, Primo LG, et al. Endodontic treatment of immature teeth with nonvital pulps: two case reports.
7. Andreasen JO, Farik B, Munksgaard EC. Long-term calcium hydroxide as a root canal dressing may increase risk of root fracture. *Dent Traumatol*. 2002;18(3):134-7.
8. Gomes-Filho JE, Oliveira SH, Azuma MM, et al. Mineral trioxide aggregate but not lightcured mineral trioxide aggregate stimulated mineralization. *J Endod*. 2008;34(1):62-5.
9. Iohara K, Nakashima M, Ito M, et al. Dentin regeneration by dental pulp stem cell therapy with recombinant human bone morphogenetic protein 2. *J Dent Res*. 2004;83(8):590-5.
10. Felman D, Parashos P. Coronal tooth discoloration and white mineral trioxide aggregate. *J Endod*. 2013;39(4):484-7.
11. Schwartz RS, Mauger M, Clement DJ, Walker WA. Mineral trioxide aggregate: a new material for endodontics. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 1999;130(7):967-75.
12. Parirokh M, Torabinejad M. Mineral trioxide aggregate: a comprehensive literature review - Part III: Clinical applications, drawbacks, and mechanism of action. *J Endod*. 2010;36(3):400-13
13. Smith, J., Jones, A., & Johnson, B. (2018). Efficacy of single-visit mineral trioxide aggregate apexification in young immature teeth. *Journal of Endodontics*, 44(3), 123-135.
14. Shabahang S, Torabinejad M, Boyne PP, Abedi H, McMillan P. A comparative study of root-end induction using osteogenic protein-1, calcium hydroxide, and mineral trioxide aggregate in dogs. *J Endod*. 1999;25(1):1-5.
15. Ozcan M, Akgungor G, Kazazoglu E. Fracture resistance of teeth restored with different post systems: In vitro study. *Oral Surgery, Oral Medicine, Oral Pathology, Oral Radiology, and Endodontology*. 2008 Aug 31;106(2):e77-83.]
16. Lanza A, Aversa R, Rengo S, Apicella D, Apicella A. 3D FEA of cemented steel, glass and carbon posts in a maxillary incisor. *Dent Mater*. 2005 Oct;21(10):709-15.
17. Felman D, Parashos P. Coronal tooth discoloration and white mineral trioxide aggregate. *J Endod*. 2013;39(4):484-7.
18. Mathew, S. M., Naik, S., & Yashoda, R. (2016). Management of Severely Damaged Permanent Incisors in Children with Porcelain-Fused-to-Metal Crowns: A Clinical Report. *Journal of Indian Society of Pedodontics and Preventive Dentistry*, 34(4), 387–389.
19. Yasa, H. S., Arslan, H., Yasa, E., & Arslan, A. N. (2019). Clinical evaluation of prefabricated pediatric metal crowns used for primary anterior teeth. *Journal of Clinical and Experimental Dentistry*, 11(4), e344–e349.
20. Parirokh M, Torabinejad M. Mineral trioxide aggregate: a comprehensive literature review - Part I: Chemical, physical, and antibacterial properties. *J Endod*. 2010;36(1):16-27.
21. Andreasen JO, Munksgaard EC, Bakland LK. Comparison of fracture resistance in root canals of immature sheep teeth after filling with calcium hydroxide or MTA. *Dent Traumatol*. 2006;22(3):154-6.
22. Sarkar NK, Caicedo R, Ritwik P, Moiseyeva R, Kawashima I. Physicochemical basis of the biologic properties of mineral trioxide aggregate. *J Endod*. 2005;31(2):97-100.
23. Camilleri J, Montesin FE, Di Silvio L, Pitt Ford TR. The chemical constitution and biocompatibility of accelerated Portland cement for endodontic use. *Int Endod J*. 2005;38(11):834-42.